

Application of starch-stabilized silver nanoparticles as a colorimetric sensor for mercury (II) in 0.005 mol/L nitric acid

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ABSTRACT

A sensitive and selective Hg^{2+} optical sensor has been developed based on redox interaction of Hg^{2+} with starch-coated silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) in the presence of $0.005 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$. The relative intensity of localized surface plasmon absorption band of AgNPs at 406 nm is linearly dependent on the concentration of Hg^{2+} ions with positive slope for the concentration range ($0\text{-}12.5 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) or negative slope for the concentration range ($25\text{-}500 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Experiments performed demonstrated that metal ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+}) do not interfere under the same conditions, due to the absence of oxidative activity of these ions, which guarantees the high selectivity of the proposed optical sensor toward Hg^{2+} ions. The limits of detection and quantification were found to be $0.9 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $2.7 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively, relative standard deviations varied in the range 9-12 % for Hg content from 0.9 to $12.5 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 5-9% for Hg levels from 25 to $500 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The method was validated by analysis of CRM Estuarine Water BCR – 505. Possible mechanism of interaction between Ag NPs and Hg^{2+} for both concentration ranges was proposed on the base of UV-vis, TEM and SAED analyses.

Keywords: Silver nanoparticles, Starch coating, Hg^{2+} ions, Sensor, Localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR)

1. Introduction

Monitoring of toxic metals in aquatic ecosystems is important analytical task as far as these contaminants adversely affect the environment and have serious medical effects on human health. One of the most harmful pollutants among them is Hg, which is still released in the environment and widely distributed in air, water and soil [1]. At very low concentrations Hg affects human's health, causing a variety of diseases to the heart, kidneys, brain, nervous and endocrine systems [2]. Naturally occurring levels of mercury in groundwater and surface water are less than $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, although local mineral deposits may produce higher levels in ground waters. Essential quality standard for Hg maximum permissible limit of $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ has been adopted at EU level and requires regular monitoring of Hg content in drinking waters. It is well known that Hg exists in natural waters as different species: Hg^0 , methylHg and inorganic Hg (II), however dominant toxic species in drinking waters is Hg (II). Various instrumental methods and techniques have been developed for Hg determination at low environmentally relevant concentrations like atomic absorption/emission spectrometry (AAS/AES) [3], atomic fluorescence spectrometry (AFS) [4, 5] and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) [6, 7]. In spite of being very sensitive and precise for Hg determination, these methods often require time-consuming sample preparation step as well as expensive instrumentation. Various colorimetric assays (based on the use of sensitive chromophores or fluorophores [8-11], polymers [12, 13], oligonucleotides [14, 15], DNA [16, 17] and metal nanoparticles [18-20]) have been developed and reported in the literature as convenient and simple alternative methods for the detection of target analytes without the requirement of sophisticated apparatus.

Metal nanoparticles have unique properties and applications in numerous fields, which are attributed to the collective dipole oscillation known as Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) [21]. This phenomenon makes them very desirable for colorimetric sensing of Hg^{2+} ions because the interaction between the nanoparticles and the analyte changes the intensity and/or position of the absorption band in the visible spectrum, which often might be observed with a naked eye [22]. The limitations observed for these systems are mainly connected with poor selectivity, high detection limit for Hg (II), complicated synthesis of the probe materials or complicated analytical procedures.

In this study, we present a new colorimetric assay for Hg^{2+} ions in $0.005 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$ using starch-stabilized silver nanoparticles (Ag NPs). A change in the absorbance strength is expected as a result of the redox interaction between Ag NPs and either Hg^{2+} ions or NO_3^- ions. The Hg concentration determines which of these two redox reactions dominates as the two

oxidants compete with each other for Ag oxidation. In this way detection of very low environmentally relevant Hg contents are possible. Several sensing systems have been already reported based on the interaction between Ag NPs and Hg (II) ions [23-32] however detailed study of Hg behavior in the presence of another competitive oxidant is rarely performed and discussed. Dual functional sensor for determination of Hg and H₂O₂ has been developed based on similar approach - addition of H₂O₂ to a mixture of Ag NPs and Hg (II) ions [33]. The method presented in this study, however, differs not only as a mechanism of the process, but also as a behavior of Hg²⁺ ions at very low concentrations (below 25 µg L⁻¹) towards Ag NPs in the presence of NO₃⁻ ions as a second oxidant. Simple and fast analytical procedure for determination of Hg in drinking waters is developed and verified by the analysis of certified reference material.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Apparatus

UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded on an Evolution 300 spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA) within the 200–800 nm range using quartz cuvettes with 1 cm optical path length. High-purity water was used as a reference sample for background absorption. The morphology and particle sizes were examined using a high resolution transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEOL JEM-2100 operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV). Volume of 5 µl AgNPs suspension was placed on a carbon-covered copper grid for TEM and air-dried. The histogram of Ag NPs size distribution and mean diameter of nanoparticles were determined by counting at least 200 nanoparticles from the different TEM images using Image J software. Some structural details of the nanoparticles were analyzed using the high-resolution TEM image and SAED pattern. The zeta (ζ) potential of nanoparticles was measured with a Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern) instrument.

2.2. Chemicals

All chemicals used were of analytical-reagent grade and all aqueous solutions were prepared in high-purity water (Millipore Corp., Milford, MA, USA). Silver nitrate (AgNO₃, 99.8 %), soluble starch, sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 99 %), nitric acid (HNO₃, 65 %), salts of the different cations studied (NaCl, KCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂, Pb(NO₃)₂, ZnCl₂, CuCl₂, NiCl₂, CdCl₂, CoCl₂, FeCl₃) from Merck, Germany, pharmaceutical grade D-(+) glucose – from Alfa Aesar, Germany were used. Stock standard solution for Hg AAS, Trace CEPTTM, 998 µg mL⁻¹ in 2

mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ (Sigma–Aldrich, USA) was used to prepare a working standard solution of 1000 µg L⁻¹ Hg²⁺ in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃. Standard solutions for Hg within the concentration range of 0-1000 µg L⁻¹ were prepared weekly by serial dilution of this solution in 0.01 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ aqueous solution. All diluted Hg solutions were stored in dark glass flasks and kept refrigerated at 4°C.

2.3. Synthesis and characterisation of silver nanoparticles

The synthesis of Ag NPs follows a green synthetic procedure as described in our previous study [34]. The silver nanoparticles were obtained through a reduction reaction of silver nitrate with D-glucose as a reducing agent in the presence of starch as a stabilizer and suitable sodium hydroxide amount as a reaction catalyst. Briefly, 24 ml 0.001 M AgNO₃ and 48 ml 0.2% solution of starch were mixed and left for at least 15 minutes to form a complex under an ultrasonic treatment (ultrasonic bath - power 100 W, frequency 38 MHz). After that, 720 µL 0.1 M D-glucose was added and sonicated for 5 minutes. The reaction was started by the addition of 3.6 ml 0.1 M NaOH and continued for one hour at constant temperature (30°C) in an ultrasonic bath to assure the homogeneous formation of the silver nanoparticles.

The as-prepared AgNPs were purified and concentrated three times by ultracentrifugation (90 min, 14 000 rpm). The dispersion obtained was denoted as a stock solution of Ag NPs and used in the experiments for colorimetric determination of Hg²⁺ ions. The Ag NPs stock solution was kept in a dark glass flask at room temperature and was homogenized by an ultrasonic bath for 30 min prior to each experiment.

2.4. Colorimetric detection of Hg²⁺ ions

The colorimetric detection of Hg²⁺ ions via starch-stabilized silver nanoparticles was conducted as follow: an aliquot of 200 µL Ag NPs stock solution and 300 µL high purity water were consecutively added into a small quartz cuvette, followed by addition of 500 µL Hg²⁺ solution with varying concentration. The resulting mixture was equilibrated by stirring on Vortex for an optimum incubation time and then the UV-vis spectrum in the wavelength range of 200-800 nm was recorded. In order to investigate the sensitivity of colorimetric assay towards other ions, starch-stabilized Ag NPs were allowed to interact under the same conditions with 50 µmol L⁻¹ solutions of alkali (Na⁺, K⁺), alkaline earth (Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺), Pb²⁺ and transition-metal ions (Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Fe³⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺) (separately for each ion). Resulting solutions were monitored by optical absorption spectroscopy.

2.5. Determination of Hg in tap/underground water

Tap/underground water sample 20 mL was filtered through a 0.45 μm filter and acidified with HNO_3 until pH in the range 2-2.3. Sample aliquot of 500 μL was transferred in quartz cuvette, 200 μL stock solution of Ag NPs was added and mixture was stirred by Vortex. After the optimum incubation time of 5 min, the UV-vis absorbance was measured at 407 nm. Parallel sample aliquot of 250 μL is diluted twice with 0.005 mol L^{-1} HNO_3 and passed through the procedure described above. The response of this sample (increase or decrease, related to original one, Fig. 4) is used to distinguish the low from the high concentration range of Hg and to choose appropriate calibration curve.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of Ag NPs

The UV-vis absorption spectrum of starch-stabilized Ag NPs, recorded at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$, is shown on Fig. 1 (inset). A single and sharp SPR band appears at 407 nm, which indicates the formation of particles with nanometer-sized dimensions. This is further confirmed by the TEM observation and size distribution histogram, shown on Fig. 1.

Figure 1: TEM image of starch-stabilized silver nanoparticles; insets: UV-vis absorption spectrum and digital photographs (left), high-resolution TEM image of single nanoparticles and histogram of nanoparticle size distribution (right).

The spherical-like Ag NPs exhibit a relatively narrow size distribution with a mean diameter of 15.4 ± 3.9 nm. In addition to the nanospheres, some typical polyhedral nanoparticles (multiple twined nanocrystals) can be easily observed. The crystalline nature of Ag NPs is clearly observed on HRTEM image on Fig. 1 (inset) and proved by the lattice characterization, e.g. the spacing between the individual lattice fringes of 0.235 nm, which corresponds to (111) plane lattice spacing of pure silver. The colloidal stability of starch-coated Ag NPs is confirmed by the ζ -potential value of -25.3 ± 1.3 mV measured in 0.001 mol L^{-1} KCl at pH 6.8.

3.2. The optimization of colorimetric sensing of Hg^{2+}

Several parameters were investigated systematically in order to establish optimal conditions for the direct colorimetric detection of Hg^{2+} ions. As a first step, the pH value was adjusted taking into account the analysis of real samples and HNO_3 which is typically used for water sample preservation. The experiments performed showed that 0.005 mol L^{-1} HNO_3 ensured highest sensitivity and could be accepted as an optimal sample media. In order to evaluate the optimum contact time, the kinetic of interaction between Ag NPs and Hg^{2+} ions in the presence of 0.005 mol L^{-1} nitric acid was followed within one hour by measurements of UV-vis absorbance. A typical evolution of UV-vis absorbance spectrum with time, due to the interaction of Ag NPs with $400 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Hg^{2+} solution and respective color change of the Ag NPs dispersion, are shown on Fig. 2.

Figure 2: (a) Evolution of UV-vis absorbance spectrum of Ag NPs and (b) Color change of the Ag NPs dispersion upon the addition of $400 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Hg^{2+} in the presence of 0.005 mol L^{-1} HNO_3

The changes that occurred in the LSPR absorption band of Ag NPs reflect on the colour of the samples, which can be seen even with a naked eye. It is seen that the sensor's response is significant during the first five minutes of the reaction process and a negligible change in the absorption intensity is observed over time. This fact allows a convenient analytical detection of Hg^{2+} ions within only five minutes.

As a next step, the sensitivity and applicability of starch coated AgNPs for quantitative determination of Hg^{2+} ions under the defined optimal conditions was studied. The colorimetric response and LSPR band behavior were monitored as a function of Hg^{2+} concentrations, ranged from 0 to $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in the presence of $0.005 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$. (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: UV Vis absorption responses of starch-stabilized Ag-NPs recorded 5 min after the addition of Hg^{2+} ion solution with various concentrations: (a) 0-12.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Hg^{2+} and (b) 25-500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Hg^{2+} in the presence of $0.005 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$.

As seen from the UV-Vis absorbance spectra (5 minutes incubation time), the addition of 0.005 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ results in a considerable decrease of the intensity of Ag NPs characteristic plasmon band at 407 nm accompanied by a slight blue shift (Fig. 3a). In addition, a shoulder band appears at the wavelength range of 450-600 nm. The increase of Hg²⁺ concentration from 0 to 12.5 µg L⁻¹ in 0.005 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ leads to a gradual increase of the intensity of characteristic plasmon band of Ag NPs at 407 nm and its value gradually approximates to the absorption intensity of blank nanoparticle solution (without both NO₃⁻ and Hg²⁺ ions). In addition, the intensity of shoulder band decreases with increasing intensity of the main plasmon absorbance band. The spectra show a clear isosbestic point at 445 nm upon addition of Hg²⁺ in 0.005 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃, demonstrating that the aggregation of Ag NPs is directly related to the concentration of Hg²⁺. Contrariwise, a gradual decrease of the intensity of characteristic plasmon band of the Ag NPs at 407 nm is observed for the Hg concentration range from 25 to 500 µg L⁻¹. The spectra presented in Fig 3b also show that the decrease of intensity of the absorbance maximum at 407 nm is accompanied with a slight blue shift, which is strengthened for the higher concentrations of Hg²⁺ ions. This phenomenon is already reported and described as a change of the refractive index of the particles and the formation of a mercury layer around Ag NPs, yielding amalgam-like structure [25, 35,36]. It might be suggested that for the first Hg concentration range (0-12.5 µg L⁻¹) a redox reaction proceeds between zero-valent silver (Ag⁰) and either Hg²⁺ or NO₃⁻ ions. The values of standard electrode potentials of the components in the system confirm this suggestion: E₀ (Ag⁺/Ag⁰) = 0.799 V; E₀ (Hg²⁺/Hg⁰) = 0.854 V; E₀ (NO₃⁻/NH₄⁺) = 0.864 V. Because the standard electrode potential of NO₃⁻/NH₄⁺ is commensurable with that of Hg²⁺/Hg⁰, two competitive oxidising agents are involved in the studied sensing system. The most probable explanation for the decrease of LSPR band intensity in the presence of 0.005 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ and further increase upon addition of Hg²⁺ ions (Fig. 3a) is that at low Hg²⁺ concentrations, the oxidative effect of NO₃⁻ ions toward surface silver atoms is dominant. In the presence of higher concentrations of Hg²⁺ (Fig. 3b) the surface of nanoparticles is protected by the layer of Ag-Hg-amalgam due to the sorption and reduction of positively charged Hg²⁺ on the surface of negatively charged AgNPs followed by amalgamation. In this way, the surface of Ag NPs is inaccessible for oxidation by NO₃⁻. Evidently, within the range of 25-500 µg L⁻¹ Hg²⁺, the main redox interaction is between the Ag NPs and Hg²⁺ ions. Such behavioural dissimilarities of the analyte (Hg²⁺) for different concentration ranges have not been observed and reported in the previous studies on Ag NPs-based optical sensing system for Hg²⁺ colorimetric detection. We have to point out, however,

that none of these reports mention the acidity of the reaction media, which most probably determines oxidizing power of reagents in the system.

For quantitative determination of Hg^{2+} the change of the intensity of LSPR band maximum of silver nanoparticles at 407 nm upon the addition of analyte with various concentrations was estimated as a ratio A_t/A_0 , where A_0 corresponds to the intensity of the absorbance maximum of blank AgNPs solution (without both NO_3^- and Hg^{2+} ions) and A_t corresponds to the intensity of the absorbance maximum of silver nanoparticles 5 min after the addition of Hg^{2+} standard solutions (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Plot of A_t/A_0 as a function of the Hg^{2+} concentration over the ranges of (a) 0-12.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and (b) 25-500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in the presence of 0.005 mol L^{-1} HNO_3 .

As indicated in Fig.4a and Fig.4b, linear correlations exist between the relative value of the absorbance maximum intensity and the concentration of Hg^{2+} over the concentration ranges $0\text{-}12.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($A = 0.7814 + 1.30 \times 10^{-2}c$ with $R^2 = 0.995$) and $25\text{-}500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($A = 0.991 - 5.90 \times 10^{-4}c$ with $R^2 = 0.993$), respectively. As a conclusion, the optical sensor studied using starch-stabilized Ag-NPs ensures a linear response over the concentration range from 0.9 to $12.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ which covers all environmentally relevant concentrations of Hg and might be used for fast screening of Hg in the aquatic environment. The second concentration range from 25 to $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Hg^{2+} , can be successfully applied for the determination of Hg in highly contaminated and rarely found industrial waste waters.

3.3. Selectivity of Hg^{2+} optical sensing by starch-coated AgNPs

From analytical point of view, it is very important to define the selectivity of proposed system for colorimetric Hg^{2+} determination. This has been evaluated through testing the response of the assay to various environmentally relevant metal ions including Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} under the same conditions as in the case of Hg^{2+} . The optical response of Ag NPs to the tested ions (concentration level of $50 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) after 5 min of their additions (separately for each ion) is illustrated in Fig. 5. For comparison the optical response of of Ag NPs to the Hg^{2+} ions at a concentration level of $2.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ is also presented.

Figure 5: Colorimetric response of starch-stabilized Ag-NPs recorded 5 min after the addition of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ metal ions.

It is easy to observe that all other metal ions produce much weaker signal (almost at baseline level) except Fe^{3+} which shows a modest interference. The reason is that only Hg^{2+} can be reduced by surface atoms of Ag NPs to form stable Ag-Hg amalgam. The addition of Fe^{3+} resulted in tiny intensity decrease and red-shift of the absorption band. This effect could be interpreted in terms of Fe (III) complexation with oxidized species of carbohydrates (starch and glucose) which are sorbed on the surface of silver nanoparticles [37].

3.4. Mechanism of interaction between Ag NPs and Hg^{2+}

To elucidate the mechanism of sensing activity of the starch-coated AgNPs toward Hg^{2+} ions the nanoparticles were examined before and after Hg^{2+} exposure using TEM with SAED observations. Figure 6 shows TEM micrograph with the corresponding SAED pattern obtained from agglomerate formed during interaction of AgNPs with Hg^{2+} solution at concentration of $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

Figure 6: (a) TEM image (scale bar is 20 nm) and (b) corresponding SAED pattern of starch-coated silver nanoparticles after treatment by Hg^{2+} solution at concentration of $500 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in the presence of $0.005 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$.

As can be seen from Fig 6a, the nanoparticles are of varying sizes and there is a large distribution after Hg^{2+} exposure. The TEM image shows a larger particle, which is surrounded by smaller particles. It seems that larger particles are undergoing Ostwald ripening. Similar observation is already reported for gold nanoparticles utilized for mercury removal from drinking water [38] and for colorimetric detection of Hg^{2+} ions using the AgNPs embedded in cyclodextrin–silicate composite [39].

The data from the analysis of SAED pattern (Fig. 6b) are summarized with interpretation accuracy of 1% in Table 1. The analysis shows the existence of Ag₂Hg₃ amalgam (PDF 65-3156) and Ag (PDF 89-3722) as main phases in the aggregated mass formed during the interaction of starch-coated Ag NPs with Hg²⁺ solution. Some impurities of metallic Hg (PDF 01-1017) are also detected.

Table 1: SAED data of Ag NPs aggregate formed after exposure of silver nanoparticles to Hg²⁺ solution at concentration of 500 μg L⁻¹ in the presence of 0.005 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃.

(hkl)_f—double electron diffraction effects; SAED interpretation: accuracy 1%

d (Å ^o)	Relative intensity	Ag	Ag	Ag ₂ Hg ₃
		PDF 89-3722 a = 4.0855(1) Å SG Fm $\bar{3}$ m	PDF 87-0598 a = 2.8862 Å, c = 10.000 Å P6 ₃ /mmc	PDF 65-3156 a = 10.0506 Å SG I23
2.438	s	-	101	(410) _f
2.136	s	-	-	332
1.506	s	-	-	622
1.287	s	(310) _f	-	237
1.057	w	-	205	930
0.979	w	(410) _f	-	059

s — strong; w —weak

On the base of TEM/SAED results, a multistep interaction of Hg²⁺ ions with the silver nanoparticles could be inferred. The interaction involves: (i) The electrostatic attraction between negatively charged silver nanoparticles and positively charged Hg²⁺ species, decreasing the distance between nanoparticles; (ii) Adsorption of Hg²⁺ ions on the surface of Ag NPs and their reduction to Hg⁰ by the surface Ag atoms. Simultaneously obtained Ag⁺ ions diffuse into the solution; (iii) Amalgamation of the freshly generated mercury atoms with the surface Ag atoms [25, 32, 39]; (iv) The interaction of Hg²⁺ with Ag NPs decreases surface charges of nanoparticles, leading to their destabilization and aggregation. The later one is confirmed by the shape-evolution of Ag NPs observed on Fig. 6a. Suggested mechanism of optical sensing of Hg²⁺ by starch-coated silver nanoparticles is illustrated on Fig. 7.

Table 2: Comparison of different methods using silver nanoparticles as colorimetric sensing probe for Hg²⁺ determination

Sensing probe	Linear concentration range	Detection limit	Ref.
Starch-stabilized Ag NPs	50 nmol L ⁻¹ -5000 nmol L ⁻¹	25 nmol L ⁻¹	[23]
Unmodified Ag NPs stabilized with extract of soap-root plant	10-100 μmol L ⁻¹	2.2 μmol L ⁻¹	[26]
Gum kondagogu-stabilized Ag NPs	50-500 nmol L ⁻¹	50 nmol L ⁻¹ (LOQ)	[31]
Citrate-capped Ag NPs	0.02 nmol L ⁻¹ - 0.9 μmol L ⁻¹	-	[33]
1-dodecanethiol-capped Ag nanoprisms upon the presence of iodides	10-4000 nmol L ⁻¹	3.3 nmol L ⁻¹	[40]
Poly(vinylpyrrolidone)-stabilized Ag NPs	1 nmol L ⁻¹ -30 μmol L ⁻¹	1 nmol L ⁻¹	[41]
Carrageenan-functionalized Ag/AgCl NPs	1-100 μmol L ⁻¹	1 μmol L ⁻¹	[42]
Starch-coated AgNPs in the presence of 0.005 mol L ⁻¹ HNO ₃	4.5-2500 nmol L ⁻¹	4.5 nmol L ⁻¹	this work

For partial validation of procedure, a CRM Estuarine Water BCR – 505 was analyzed. Three sample aliquots of 800 μL we analyzed according to the proposed analytical procedure. The result of 0.73 ± 0.08 nmol L⁻¹ Hg was in reasonable agreement with the (‘additional material information) value of 0.69 nmol kg⁻¹ Hg (138 μg L⁻¹).

4. Conclusions

Simple, fast and low cost analytical procedure is developed for easy and sensitive quantification of Hg²⁺ ions in the presence of 0.005 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ by using starch-coated AgNPs as a LSPR-based optical sensor. The Hg²⁺ sensing is based on the optical response (change in the absorbance strength of LSPR band) of silver nanoparticles depending on the Hg²⁺ ion concentration. Possible mechanism of interaction between Ag NPs and Hg²⁺ was proposed. An accurate and reliable determination of Hg is achieved in two concentration ranges of 0.9 – 12.5 μg L⁻¹ and 25 – 500 μg L⁻¹. The limits of detection and quantification achieved were 0.9 μg L⁻¹ and 2.7 μg L⁻¹, respectively, relative standard deviations varied in the range 9-12 % for Hg content from 0.9 to 12.5 μg L⁻¹ and 5-9% for Hg levels from 25 to 500 μg L⁻¹. The LSPR-based optical sensor for Hg (II) might be used for simple and fast *on site* screening of sources for abstraction of drinking water and for Hg determination in waste waters.

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